

REPORT ON REMOTISATION AND SIMULATION

TOOLS

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Abstract

The AgrifoodTEF project is a collaborative network of test and validation infrastructures across Europe, designed to support Agri-Food technology companies in the near-product development of AI and robotics solutions within real-world agricultural settings. The project aims to bridge the gap between cutting-edge research and practical applications, enhancing efficiency and sustainability in agriculture while meeting the stringent usability and economic needs of end-users. Rooted in existing experimental farms and facilities, which are now operational, the project fosters a scalable approach to ensuring food security in the EU by engaging stakeholders and leveraging expert knowledge in AI and robotics. This document presents an overview of simulation and remotisation tools that facilitate the creation, visualization, and manipulation of virtual models of agrifood systems, as well as the remote control and monitoring of real-world processes.

This report is the third annual update on the progress made in identifying and cataloging simulation and remotisation tools utilized by AgrifoodTEF project partners. This third version of the report includes fourteen simulation tools and three remotisation tools. For many of the tools there are case studies of how the tool is used, in an agricultural context, with analysis of the tool's pros and cons. This third report also includes links to AgrifoodTEF services that use the tools.

Introduction

The AgrifoodTEF project represents a significant initiative aimed at enhancing the agricultural sector through the integration of advanced technologies, particularly artificial intelligence (AI) and robotics. As a collaborative network of test and validation infrastructures across Europe, AgrifoodTEF supports technology companies in the near-product development of innovative solutions tailored for real-world agricultural applications.

- The primary objective of AgrifoodTEF is to bridge the gap between cutting-edge research and practical implementation, fostering sustainable agricultural practices that meet the growing demands for efficiency and productivity. This initiative is particularly relevant in the context of increasing global food security challenges, as it leverages existing operational experimental farms and facilities. Standards for dataset creation, data sovereignty, and algorithm interoperability will be guided by GAIA-X, with representatives from various agricultural domains in Europe contributing to this framework.
- Each TEF-node will operate independently with a sustainable business model tailored to regional needs, while collectively adhering to shared guidelines and standards that facilitate cross-regional collaboration. The aim is to position Europe as a leader in the adoption of innovative, technology-driven solutions for Agri-Food, enhancing efficiency in primary production akin to the advancements achieved during the Green Revolution.

This report serves as the third annual update on the progress made in identifying and cataloging simulation and remotisation tools utilized by project partners. It introduces the concepts and tools that are evaluated and used within AgrifoodTEF. These tools are essential for creating, visualizing, and manipulating virtual models of agrifood systems, as well as for enabling remote control and monitoring of agricultural processes. The insights gathered from this report will not only highlight the current landscape of tools in use but also provide a foundation for future developments and enhancements in agricultural technology, aligning with the objectives of other tasks within the project. This third version of the report includes fourteen simulation tools and three remotisation tools (compared to ten plus three in the previous report). This third report includes more detailed and specific descriptions of the tools and how the tools are used or planned to be used in AgrifoodTEF services. For many of the tools there are case studies of how the tool is used, in an agricultural example, with analysis of the tool's pros and cons.

Outline

This report details the findings and methodologies related to the simulation and remotisation tools utilized within the AgrifoodTEF project. The Simulation Software section provides an overview of various tools, including their functionalities and applications, supported by case studies that illustrate their effectiveness in agricultural contexts. The Remotisation Software section similarly explores tools that facilitate remote control and monitoring of agricultural processes, detailing their integration and practical use cases. The Discussion and Future work section synthesizes the key findings from the previous sections, highlighting their implications for the agricultural sector and identifying areas for improvement. This section also outlines the plans for ongoing evaluation and development of these tools, emphasizing the project's commitment to continuous enhancement and adaptation to meet evolving agricultural challenges.

AgrifoodTEF simulation and remotisation tool surveys

As part of the activities to identify simulation and remotisation tools, RISE has conducted two surveys to understand the current landscape and future potential of these tools as key enablers in agricultural technology. The first survey gathered insights from partners, focusing on evaluating the effectiveness, challenges, and reusability opportunities of the tools. The second survey collected input for a joint knowledge base and information about how the tools are used and planned to be used in AgrifoodTEF services.

Initial AgrifoodTEF Simulation and remotization software survey

The primary objectives of the first survey were to:

- Assess application areas: Identify where simulation and remotisation tools are currently utilized within agrifood technologies.
- Evaluate adoption rates: Determine how widely these tools have been adopted by partners and their integration into existing agricultural practices.
- Determine impact: Assess the impact of these tools on improving efficiency, productivity, and sustainability in agriculture.

The survey was designed using a mix of quantitative and qualitative questions to capture detailed feedback on current tool practices, user experiences, and the number of tools in use per partner. More details about the this first survey was described in the second annual update of this report.

Second AgrifoodTEF Simulation and remotization software survey

The primary objectives of the second survey were to:

- Collect information about how the tools are used and planned to be used in AgrifoodTEF services.
- Collect input for the joint knowledge base

6. Which AgrifoodTEF service(s) currently use this tool?

Ange ditt svar

7. Why was this tool selected for the service?

- Already in use by partner
- Integration with existing systems
- Cost-effectiveness
- Open-source/community support
- Partner recommendation
- Feasibility/performance
- Annat

8. Subjective rating of tool performance in this service:

9. What are the main integration steps taken to use the tool in this service?

E.g., data pipeline development, ROS integration, AI model adaptation, interface setup

Ange ditt svar

Knowledge Base Contribution

19. Do you have a user manual, guide, tutorial for this tool?

- Yes
- No
- Cannot share - contact person available (provide contact)

Figure 1 Survey questions to collect information about tool usage in AgrifoodTEF services and to collect input to the joint knowledge base.

Simulation and remotisation tool knowledge base

We have initiated the work to collect information and to set up a dedicated simulation and remotisation tool knowledge base specific to agricultural practices. The knowledge base will be a resource for all AgrifoodTEF partners, providing detailed information on the tools' capabilities, best practices for their use, and guidelines for integration into agricultural systems.

Simulation Software

Simulation software serves as a platform for creating virtual models and environments for testing, training, and analysis purposes. These tools allow to replicate real-world scenarios within a controlled digital space, facilitating experimentation, design, and training without the constraints or risks of physical testing. Simulation tools also provide independence of seasonal influence and great repeating capacities for testing. Common applications include engineering simulations, flight and driving simulators, medical training, and 3D modeling. Simulation software often includes realistic physics engines, graphical interfaces, and support for data analysis, catering to various industries like aerospace, automotive, healthcare, and entertainment. The advantage of using simulation software is that it enables users to refine designs, train personnel, and conduct research in a cost-effective and safe manner.

Crop simulation

Unity

Unity is a cross-platform game engine developed by Unity Technologies. The engine can be used to create 2D- and 3D-games, and interactive simulations. The engine has been adopted by industries outside video gaming, such as film, automotive, architecture, engineering, and construction¹. Unity is proprietary software that offers free versions for individuals and companies. The Unity Perception package[unity-perception2022] provides a toolkit for generating large-scale datasets for computer vision training and validation. The package is open-source and licensed under Apache License Version 2.0.

Case study: Sim2real flower detection towards automated Calendula harvesting

This case study, from EV ILVO, demonstrates how synthetically generated data can aid deep learning and computer vision, and it exemplifies this in the context of automating the detection and localisation of Calendula flowers. To this end, a pipeline was created that utilises photogrammetry and a flower field simulator (using Unity) to create synthetic data of a flower field. Next, synthetic data was used to train a deep neural network to detect flowers and the transfer

¹ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Unity_\(game_engine\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Unity_(game_engine))

from simulation to reality is demonstrated on real data. This work is described in detail in the research paper by Vierbergen et al [Sim2real]. The text and Figure 2 and Figure 3 are extracts from that article.

The flower of a Calendula plant has many interesting and valuable properties. The Calendula flower can either be consumed fresh or used as a colourant in foods. Oil from the flowers, in turn, can be used in medical ointments and cosmetics. In addition, seed oil is a coveted substance for paints and coatings. Due to its properties and the wide habitat of the flower, the Calendula flower is of interest to farmers in large regions of the world. Currently, however, Calendula flowers are mainly harvested manually. This results in high labour costs which makes the cultivation of Calendulas economically not feasible in many countries. Different mechanical harvesting methods have been proposed over the past decades. One way to improve the harvest efficiency is by equipping these mechanical harvesters with robotic components to perceive the flowers, detect their height, and automatically adjust the height of the harvester. To detect the flowers, machine vision can be utilised. The use of deep learning for computer vision and object detection has gained a lot of attention in the last decade. Supervised deep learning technologies outperform older computer vision techniques. However, training a supervised deep learning algorithm often requires the availability of large, labelled datasets for training. This is especially true in the case of agricultural applications, where it is challenging to handle all possible variations that can occur, for example in illumination, background, arrangement of the objects, occurrence of weeds, and growth stage of the plants. Moreover, this makes data collection costly and creates a bottleneck for the application of deep learning in an agricultural context. To eliminate this bottleneck, the use of synthetically created data has gained a lot of attention in the past few years. Synthetic data generation has the advantages that it is possible to quickly generate scenes that are hard to capture in reality, it is inherently accompanied by pixel-perfect labels and makes quick iterations possible. In the case of agricultural applications, synthetic data generation makes it possible to create data with high variability. Environmental variables such as illumination, plant growth, shape, and texture can be determined arbitrarily in this process.

Vierbergen et al [Sim2real] present a pipeline to generate a synthetic dataset of Calendula flowers with the use of photogrammetry and the Unity game engine. To generate the synthetic images, the Unity Perception package was used. The open-source package, developed by Unity Technologies, extends the Unity Editor and engine components to generate annotated images for computer vision tasks. By using this framework, a scene was created which is made up of different layers, each filled with a certain object type. From bottom to top, the layers in the flower field simulator represent the background, leaves, flowers, illumination, and a camera. These layers are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Simulation of a flower field in Unity to generate synthetic images. The scene consists of different layers. From bottom to top: (1) background images of weeds, (2) Calendula leaves, (3) Calendula flowers, (4) point lights, and (5) a camera.

The background layer displays the soil, weeds, and shadows in the images. This layer is composed of a random selection of images from two datasets captured in Australia and Belgium. Above the background layer, the leaves of the Calendula were rendered. For each frame, a random selection of the seven leaf models was positioned at random places with a random rotation along all axes. The flowers are rendered on the third layer. In open fields, a wide variety of light conditions occurs. To simulate this, a layer with irregularly positioned point lights was added. By varying the number of point lights positioned in this layer and their position, the scene is irregularly illuminated. Positioned atop these layers is a camera which captures an image of the scene along with its corresponding annotations.

In only a short amount of time, the flower field simulator is able to create a large dataset. Figure 3 shows a few of the generated images next to images of real Calendula flowers.

Figure 3 Top: examples of real images from the captured dataset. Bottom: images generated with the proposed synthetic data pipeline.

Despite clear differences, the synthetic images can be recognised as images of a Calendula field and clearly share some characteristics with the real images. In both, the same types of objects appear: flowers and leaves of Calendula plants, soil, weeds, and varied lighting conditions. The colour distribution of both datasets share similar characteristics as well.

In the next step, a Calendula flower detector, based on a convolutional neural network, was trained on synthetic data and validated on a test set of real Calendula images. Although the flower detector has not been trained on real data, it reaches an F1 score of up to 86% on the test sets of real data. This flower detector, combined with stereo vision, enables the localisation of the flowers to automatically adjust the height of harvesters to increase harvest efficiency. More information can be found in the paper by Vierbergen et al [Sim2real].

In conclusion, leveraging the potential of synthetic data can lower the costs of collecting large datasets in uncontrolled environments and can accelerate the development of precision agricultural applications. As a final contribution, all collected and generated data for this study was made available on Zenodo.org [Sim2real dataset] as a contribution to future research on precision agriculture. The synthetic dataset follows the Synthetic Optimized Labeled Objects (SOLO) Dataset Schema, as defined in the Unity Perception package. For completeness, the data scheme is also included in the upload.

Summary:

- **Used by:** EV ILVO
- **Link to the website:** <https://unity.com/>
- **Tool effectiveness:** Unity is effective for creating realistic simulations and generating synthetic datasets for training computer vision models. Its use in the Sim2real flower detection project demonstrates its capability to bridge the gap between simulated and real-world agricultural data, achieving an F1 score of up to 86% on test sets of real data. The detection model determined the 3D positions of flowers with an average error of 6 ± 5.1 mm in predicting flower height. Using the tool, it took only 20 minutes to generate a training set of

15,000 synthetic images on a laptop with an Intel i7-8550U CPU and a Radeon Pro WX 3100 GPU. EV ILVO gave a score of 5 in the survey question of how likely they would recommend Unity on a scale of 1 to 5 where 1 means 'not at all' and 5 means 'very likely'.

- **Integration strategies:** Unity integrates with various machine learning frameworks and tools. It can be used to generate labeled datasets that can be used to train and validate machine learning models, enhancing its applicability in precision agriculture.
- **Cost analysis:** Unity is proprietary, but it offers a free version for individual users and small companies. The major costs involve the initial setup and any potential licensing fees for advanced features (e.g., high resolution 3D objects, map integration with GAIA).
- **Assumptions:** Access to high-performance computing resources to handle extensive processing required for simulation and data generation. It also requires basic understanding of game engine operations, computer vision and basic machine learning principles.
- **Skill requirement:** Technical skills in game engine operations, scripting and understanding of computer vision and machine learning concepts. There is available documentation and community support available.

Robotic simulation

Webots

Webots, developed by Cyberbotics, is an open-source, general purpose simulation software for robotics used by UniMi (University of Milan) and WUR. It provides an environment for modeling, programming, and simulating robots, designed for professional use in industries, education and research featuring GUI, a physics engine (ODE fork) and an OpenGL 3.3 rendering engine. The software supports programming in C, C++, Python, Java, MATLAB, and ROS, offering a simple API for basic robotics needs.

Case study: UniMi robotics simulation via Webots

Figure 4 The simulated robot in a small vineyard environment for testing.

Figure 5 The real robot (at a different time in the development process).

Webots is a robotics simulator that enables developers to create virtual environments, simulate sensors and actuators, and test algorithms. It is very similar to the more commonly used Gazebo simulator. UniMi developed (still in progress, but close to completion) an autonomous tracked agricultural robot for application of plant protection products using advanced variable rate technology (VRT). The robot is based on a platform provided by a company specialized in tracked vehicles, which was built on UniMi's specifications. In the very initial state of development of the project, the platform was still not available due to delays caused by the chip shortage, therefore we decided to start the development on a simulator.

Having decided to use ROS2 as the framework for the high-level functionalities of the robot, we initially considered Gazebo as a solution for the simulation, but after some tests with the example simulation models of a tracked robot²³, it was evident that the physical simulation of the interaction between the tracks and the ground was not adequate. We therefore searched for alternatives, and ultimately decided to use the Webots simulator, starting development from an example robot available at Webots GitHub⁴. The Webots simulation software, just like Gazebo, provides integration with ROS/ROS2 and is transparent to the rest of the system (i.e., as far as the rest of the software is concerned, it makes no difference whether we are using the real robot or the simulator).

The main difference in the development using the simulation software between Gazebo and Webots consists of the description of the simulation model. Gazebo uses the URDF and xacro formats to describe the robot, the sensors, and the environment. These are standardized description formats in ROS2, which can be used in other parts of a ROS2 system (for example in the visualization of the robot using the RViz software). On the other hand, in Webots, the description of the robot and the environment are specified in WBT and proto files, with a language similar to VRML. The URDF description of the robot can be manually exported by Webots starting from the WBT/PROTO description. This makes it possible to have only one description, rather than maintaining the robot description in two languages,

² Gazebo GitHub, https://github.com/gazebosim/gazebo-classic/blob/gazebo11/worlds/tracked_vehicle_simple.world

³ Gazebo GitHub, https://github.com/gazebosim/gazebo-classic/blob/gazebo11/worlds/tracked_vehicle_wheeled.world

⁴ Webots GitHub, <https://github.com/cyberbotics/webots/blob/released/projects/samples/devices/worlds/track.wbt>

although this workflow is still somewhat inefficient, since it is necessary to export the URDF description every time the WBT/PROTO files are changed.

To use Webots to develop the simulation of our robot, we used plugins for sensors when available in Webots. Although the library of ready-to-use sensors and actuators available in Webots is quite comprehensive, even including some models of real-world devices (e.g., for LIDAR sensors). Other sensors and actuators had to be developed using the C/C++ interface provided by Webots, because they were not available in the Webot library or to replicate exactly the behavior of the sensors of the real robot. Some of the sensors and actuators that we implemented ourselves, are the actuation of the track motors, reading the track motor odometry, dual-antenna GNSS compassing, and the IMU. Writing the code to implement the sensors and actuators required by our robot was not difficult thanks to the documentation of the internal functionalities of Webots, all of which have example code.

Currently, we use the simulator in conjunction with the real robot, as it allows us to test its software while developing it, which would be much more time consuming and restrictive if we were to only test it with the real robot. Additionally, the simulator allows us to test and experiment the autonomous navigation safely.

The simulated robot has equivalent measures and functionalities to the real robot with respect to the guidance and navigation, in the sense that all sensors and actuators used on the real robot are also implemented in the simulation, with the exception to the sprayer nozzles, which would require simulating the spraying physics.

As for the implemented simulation functionalities, although the physics simulation can be used to verify the overall correctness of the behavior of the control software, it is not accurate enough to represent its performance in the real setting, therefore, we still need to carry out real world tests to optimize this functionality.

As a note on the spraying simulation, although this may be possible, for example with an approximate simulation of airflow and water droplets or by measuring the region of space reached by the spray of individual nozzles, it would require substantial development time and may still not provide a sufficiently accurate representation of real-world behavior, especially considering the inaccuracy in the simulated dynamics of the vehicle which would affect the results of the spraying, and the complex interaction between the droplets and the crop's canopy.

Summary:

- **Used by:** UniMI, WUR
- **Link to the website:** <https://cyberbotics.com/>
- **Tool effectiveness:** Webots is a general-purpose simulation software for robotics. UniMI and WUR give an average score of 4 in the survey question of how likely they would recommend Webots on a scale of 1 to 5 where 1 means 'not at all' and 5 means 'very likely'.
- **Integration strategies:** Webots can be integrated into existing project workflows by using its APIs to connect with software and hardware tools making it versatile for both project and research activities. It supports various programming languages including C, C++, Python, Java and Robot Operating System (ROS).
- **Cost analysis:** Webots is free and open source.
- **Assumptions:** Access to compatible computer hardware capable of running the software.
- **Skill requirement:** Webots require basic understanding of robotics concepts and programming languages required for the simulation environment. Tutorials and user guides are available online.

Gazebo

Gazebo is an open-source 3D robotics simulator that incorporates the ODE physics engine, OpenGL rendering, and supporting code for sensor simulation and actuator control. It allows the use of various high-performance physics engines, with ODE being the default. Gazebo offers realistic rendering of environments, featuring high-quality lighting,

shadows, and textures. Additionally, it can model a variety of sensors, including laser range finders, cameras (wide-angle included), Kinect-style sensors, and more.

Figure 6 Gazebo simulator with vineyard models from the BACCHUS project repository (https://github.com/LCAS/bacchus_lcas)

Politecnico di Milano uses Gazebo to develop and test robotic navigation algorithms that exploit multimodal sensor input. A recent project at Politecnico di Milano serve as an example of how Gazebo can be used.

Case study: Using Gazebo for development of an autonomous lawn mower

In this case, we aimed to convert a robotic lawnmower prototype into a fully autonomous system capable of cutting grass in various outdoor environments. This process involved integrating sensors and developing a robust autonomous navigation system.

Several key challenges emerged during the development.

1. First, we needed to identify the optimal sensor choice and configuration without prematurely investing in expensive hardware.
2. Second, we wanted to test our localization algorithms without immediate access to the physical robot, as deploying it in the field is time-consuming and logistically challenging.
3. Finally, we needed to safely test our navigation algorithms, avoiding the risks of damaging the robot, the environment, or harming people nearby.

To address these challenges, we adopted Gazebo as one of the core tools in our development process. It allowed us to simulate the robot and its environment, facilitating sensor selection and algorithm testing in a risk-free virtual setting. Using this platform, we could experiment iteratively before transitioning to real-world trials.

Our development workflow began with creating a simulated model of the robotic lawnmower. We also designed multiple virtual environments, including open fields and photovoltaic parks, to reflect the diverse outdoor settings where the robot would eventually operate. Once the model and environments were in place, we integrated various sensors into the simulated lawnmower. For example, we tested different configurations of LiDAR sensors by adjusting

parameters such as range, field of view, and placement on the chassis, aiming to enhance the robot's perception of its surroundings.

Through these simulations, we measured the performance of the localization algorithms, using sensor fusion techniques to combine data from multiple sources and refine the robot's positioning accuracy. Additionally, we focused on testing and optimizing the autonomous navigation algorithms. By running these algorithms in the simulated environments, we could explore different parameter settings to fine-tune the system's behavior. This iterative approach helped us identify the most effective navigation strategies without risking real-world consequences. Once we achieved satisfactory results in the virtual tests, we transitioned to physical implementation. We integrated the chosen sensors into the real robotic lawnmower and deployed the software architecture. Confident in the system's reliability, we proceeded with live tests in actual agricultural fields.

Gazebo was key to the success of this project. It provided critical features such as the ability to simulate sensor perception and run complex algorithms in real time. Its open-source nature allowed us to examine its code and extend its functionalities, if necessary, which proved valuable in addressing specific project needs. Moreover, Gazebo is lightweight and resource-efficient compared to other simulators, enabling us to use it on standard workstations without the need for specialized hardware.

While Gazebo was highly effective for our robotic lawnmower project, we acknowledge its limitations when dealing with more complex environments that involve intricate physical interactions between the robot and the surroundings. For instance, simulating deformable objects, such as plants and the detachment of crops during selective harvesting with a robotic arm, would present significant challenges. Gazebo's capabilities in simulating such interactions are limited and would require more advanced or specialized simulators.

Overall, Gazebo proved to be an indispensable tool in our development process. Its flexibility, accessibility, and ability to simulate real-world conditions allowed us to extensively refine our system before deploying it in the field. Despite some limitations in simulating complex physical interactions, it was highly effective for this project, and we achieved our results with it.

Summary:

- **Used by:** Politecnico di Milano, WUR, FBK, ILVO
- **Link to the website:** <https://gazebosim.org/>
- **AgriFoodTEF services that use the tool:** "Preparation of computational test environment"
 - <https://agrifoodtef.eu/catalogue-of-services/preparation-computational-test-environment>
- **Platform features:** Gazebo uses physics engines like ODE, Bullet and DART to simulate realistic physical interactions. It can support multi-robot simulations and is highly customizable.
- **Tool effectiveness:** Gazebo enables physical designs in realistic virtual environments with a variety of sensor streams. The tool provides advanced 3D graphics, precise physics engine and multimodal sensors. Gazebo makes it possible to test control strategies in a safe virtual environment. As an example, Politecnico di Milano uses Gazebo to develop and test robotic navigation algorithms, and gave a score of 4 in the survey question of 'how likely they would recommend Gazebo' on a scale of 1 to 5 where 1 means 'not at all' and 5 means 'very likely'.
- **Integration strategies:** Gazebo can be integrated with software tools and robot operating systems (ROS) through its APIs and plugins to test robot operations in a safe virtual environment.
- **Cost analysis:** The tool is open source.
- **Assumptions:** Access to computer system with sufficient processing power and graphics capabilities to handle 3D simulations.
- **Skill requirement:** Gazebo requires a basic understanding of robotics and simulation principles. There is documentation available online and a community for support (<https://community.gazebosim.org>)

- **Limitations:** Performance may degrade with large-scale simulations, requiring high-end hardware. Also, environmental effects, such as rain, are not natively simulated.

ROS2

ROS2 is an open-source framework consisting of libraries, tools, and middleware designed to simplify the development of robotic applications. It provides developer tools for simulation, visualization, debugging, and deployment. ROS2 is a middleware to simulate and program robots. It comes with many packages such as Rviz for visualization and open-source robotics simulator like Gazebo/Gazebo-Sim. Moreover, ROS2 can be integrated with various simulation tools publicly available like Webots, CoppeliaSim, and Unity3D.

Summary:

- **Used by:** INRIA
- **Link to the website:** <https://docs.ros.org/en/humble/Installation.html>
- **Cost analysis:** Open source
- **Tool effectiveness:** Provides developer tools for simulation, visualization, debugging, and deployment of robotic applications
- **Integration strategies:** ROS2 comes with many packages such as Rviz for visualization and the robotics Gazebo/Gazebo-Sim. ROS2 can be integrated with various simulation tools like Webots, CoppeliaSim, and Unity3D.
- **AgriFoodTEF services that use the tool:** INRIA utilise robots programmed with ROS, to do data acquisition, and mobility algorithms testing and validation in AgrifoodTEF services.
 - Provision of general-purpose datasets via multisensory ground robot
 - <https://agrifoodtef.eu/catalogue-of-services/provision-general-purpose-datasets-multisensory-ground-robot>
 - Testing and evaluation of mobility algorithms with ground robots
 - <https://agrifoodtef.eu/catalogue-of-services/testing-and-evaluation-mobility-algorithms-ground-robots>

4D-Virtualiz / 4DV-SIMULATOR

4D-Virtualiz is a proprietary software used by LNE. The software simulates one or more robotic models into a 3D world. It has a physics engine which computes the world dynamics and produces accurate simulation of robot movements and its interactions with the environment. It can be used to assess the system robustness against challenging situations and produce stress tests, simulate sensor degradation, etc. LNE has developed a platform named Laboratory of Evaluation of AI (LE.IA) Simulation (purely numeric for virtual testing) to evaluate and assess agrifood robots using 4DV-Virtualiz to generate synthetic data of harsh environmental conditions such as foggy situations, and day/night images. A second infrastructure named LE.IA Immersion was developed for hardware-in-the-loop mixed testing of AI physical systems and models in their environment. Many scenarios including a digital twin of the Montoldre Farm (INRAE's site) currently integrate the LEIA Immersion infrastructure.

Summary:

- **Used by:** LNE
- **Link to the website:** <https://www.4d-virtualiz.com/>
- **Tool effectiveness:** 4DV-SIMULATOR is a real-time 3D simulation platform used for the development of robotic systems like vehicles, robots and drones. The tool enables realistic 3D virtual representations of operational use-cases.
- **Integration strategies:** 4D-Virtualiz integrates with various robotics software and hardware to support real-time data exchange and co-simulation with other platforms, making it suitable for diverse research and development projects.

- **Cost analysis:** 4D-Virtualiz requires a licensing fee. The cost varies based on the usage requirements and scale of the deployment. While the initial setup can be significant, the detailed simulations and robot testing capabilities can lead to cost savings by reducing the need for physical prototypes and minimizing risks in real-world testing.
- **Assumptions:** Access to high performance computing resources to handle complex simulations.
- **Skill requirement:** 4D-Virtualiz requires fundamental understanding of robotics, simulation principles and familiarity with programming. There is documentation and support available to assist practitioners.

Unreal Engine 5

Unreal Engine 5's cutting-edge capabilities make it an ideal choice for applications where photorealism is crucial. However, the latest version still lags behind its predecessor (UE4) when it comes to seamless integration with AI-related plugins. Despite this limitation, developers can leverage Unreal Engine 5's powerful features to create highly realistic environments, as demonstrated by LNE's project, which utilized UE5 to set up a photorealistic rural test site featuring a drivable vehicle surrounded by dynamic, living obstacles and traffic patterns. The use of blueprint systems and C++ event handlers allow the integration of AI systems, highlighting the potential of Unreal Engine 5 for complex simulations.

Summary:

- **Used by:** LNE, WUR
- **Link to the website:** <https://www.unrealengine.com/unreal-engine-5>
- **AgrifoodTEF services that use the tool:** Provision of a virtual playground for robots
 - <https://agrifoodtef.eu/catalogue-of-services/provision-virtual-playground-robots>
- **Tool effectiveness:** Unreal Engine (UE) is a cutting-edge game engine that enables the creation of highly realistic 3D virtual environments. With its advanced capabilities, LNE has successfully developed a simulated farm scenario where navigation and obstacle detection algorithms can effectively integrate a moving vehicle. However, despite its impressive features, the latest version 5 may lack seamless integration with some plugins. LNE gives an average score of 4 in the survey question of how likely they would recommend UE5 on a scale of 1 to 5 where 1 means 'not at all' and 5 means 'very likely'.
- **Integration strategies:** UE5 can support ROS, however its integration is very recent and can be hard to configure.
- **Cost analysis:** UE5 is free for academics use. For development studios, royalty applies to gross product revenues of \$1 million (USD) or more. Freelancers and small businesses (with gross annual revenue of less than 1 million dollars (USD)) do not pay any royalties.
- **Assumptions:** Access to high performance computing resources to handle complex simulations.
- **Skill requirement:** UE5 requires fundamental understanding of robotics, simulation principles and familiarity with programming. There is documentation and support available to assist practitioners.
- **Use case (under development by LNE):** Obstacle detection tests, following the norm NF EN ISO 18497-4 (Tractors and agricultural equipment - Safety of partially automated, semi-autonomous and autonomous machines).

ISAAC Sim

ISAAC Sim is an open-source, robotic simulation software built to address many of the most common use cases, including manipulation, navigation, and synthetic data generation for training data. It includes advanced physics simulation, photorealism and MDL (Material Definition Language) material definition support for physically based

rendering. LNE explored other simulation tools such as the ISAAC Sim to setup a robot navigation in its controlled environment. Besides a huge graphical consumption, ISAAC Sim proposes a standardized format to import robots (URDF).

Summary:

- **Used by:** LNE, WUR
- **Link to the website:** <https://developer.nvidia.com/isaac-sim>
- **Tool effectiveness:** ISAAC Sim is useful to generate synthetic data for training AI models, enhancing the development and validation process. It also provides useful simulation capabilities for robotic detailed manipulation and navigation tasks. LNE gave a score of 4 in the survey question of how likely they would recommend ISAAC Sim on a scale of 1 to 5 where 1 means 'not at all' and 5 means 'very likely'.
- **Integration strategies:** ISAAC Sim integrates with NVIDIA's ecosystem, including GPUs and deep learning frameworks. It supports ROS and other robotics middleware.
- **Cost analysis:** ISAAC Sim is freely accessible. However, optimal performance may require NVIDIA hardware, which could involve additional costs.
- **Assumptions:** Effective use of ISAAC Sim requires access to compatible NVIDIA hardware and an understanding of NVIDIA ecosystem.
- **Skill requirement:** Familiarity with robotics simulation, AI model training principles and NVIDIA's tools and platforms. There is documentation and community support available for practitioners.
- **Use case (under development by LNE):** Obstacle detection tests, following the norm NF EN ISO 18497-4 (Tractors and agricultural equipment - Safety of partially automated, semi-autonomous and autonomous machines).

Esmimi

Esmimi (Environment Simulator Minimalistic) is an open-source software tool to play "OpenSCENARIO" files. It is available both as a stand-alone application and as a shared library for linking with custom applications. In addition, some tools have been designed to support design and analysis of traffic scenarios. AstaZero uses Esmimi to visualize scenarios where the tool CARLA is used as rendering and early proof of concept simulation engine when working with perception and robotics.

Case study: Using Esmimi with CARLA for consistent test execution

AstaZero AB utilizes Esmimi to visualize scenarios within the context of autonomous driving vehicle simulation. This tool is often employed in co-simulation with the software tool CARLA. Below is an example demonstrating how AstaZero AB leverages Esmimi for testing automation functionalities.

Figure 7 Scenario simulation via Esmi

AstaZero AB was engaged to investigate the realism required in a test environment to effectively validate and verify ADAS (advanced driver assistance systems) and AD (assisted driving) functions and to ensure that these functions could be exposed to complex and challenging traffic scenarios. This project involved conducting both physical and digital tests based on scenarios from the Euro NCAP test protocols for AEB (autonomous emergency braking) performance. Subsequently, a comparison and analysis of the test results were performed.

The tests were designed based on pre-defined scenarios, each one consisting of a sequence of events outlined in OpenSCENARIO files. These files detailed the actors, event triggers, and the dynamic conditions that the scenario should follow and served as the baseline for both the physical and digital test executions.

Esmi was employed to perform the simulated tests in co-simulation with CARLA. In this configuration, Esmi managed the scenario descriptions defined in OpenSCENARIO, while CARLA provided the simulation environment, handling more complex physics and rendering. Additionally, Esmi was utilized to validate the OpenSCENARIO files during development and to facilitate the execution of the physical tests.

The validation of OpenSCENARIO files during development was conducted by visualisation. Within the co-simulation framework, Esmi acted as the scenario controller, overseeing the simulation's progression. It was responsible for triggering scenario events at the appropriate times and updating the states of all actors in alignment with the scenario description.

The use of Esmi in this example facilitated consistent test execution across both simulated and physical environments, while also enabling the validation of predefined scenarios prior to the test executions.

Esmi is an integral part of a comprehensive simulation toolchain, enabling performance and functionality testing at various stages of development. It plays a significant role in AstaZero AB's simulation toolchain and is frequently used in daily operations.

Summary:

- **Used by:** AstaZero
- **Link to the website:** <https://esmini.github.io/>

- **Tool effectiveness:** AstaZero uses Esmini to visualize automotive scenarios in combination with the tool Carla. They gave a score of 2 in the survey question of how likely they would recommend Esmini on a scale of 1 to 5 where 1 means 'not at all' and 5 means 'very likely'.
- **Integration strategies:** Esmini integrates well with other simulation tools such as CARLA to enhance visualization and scenario analysis.
- **Cost analysis:** Esmini is open-source, eliminating licensing costs.
- **Assumptions:** Access to compatible hardware capable of running the simulations efficiently.
- **Skill requirement:** It requires knowledge of traffic scenario design, software developer and python knowledge. There is available documentation and community support to help users.

CoppeliaSim VREP

CoppeliaSim (formerly V-REP) is a robotics simulator. It has an integrated development environment and is based on a distributed control architecture. CoppeliaSim is used at ILVO to simulate kinematic models of agricultural robots. This enables early detection of errors in the kinematic modelling before actual deployment on the robot platforms.

Figure 8 CoppeliaSim example.

Figure 8 shows a screenshot from a video⁵ showing the process for the CIMAT robot, having a 4WD4WS robot configuration.

Summary:

- **Used by:** ILVO
- **Link to the website:** <https://www.coppeliarobotics.com/>

⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0MwMeYQQPIE>

- **Tool effectiveness:** CoppeliaSim is useful for research and development projects in robotics as it allows simulating complex robotic systems and processes. Its distributed control architecture allows for flexible and scalable simulations.
- **Integration strategies:** CoppeliaSim integrates with multiple programming languages including Python, C/C++, Java and robotics frameworks/ROS. It also allows seamless connectivity and data exchange with other tools and systems.
- **Cost analysis:** CoppeliaSim has both free and paid versions. The free version provides all basic capabilities, while the paid version offers additional features and support tailored to different user needs and budgets.
- **Assumptions:** Access to compatible hardware and stable development environment for optimal performance.
- **Skill requirement:** Familiarity with robotics simulation and basic programming skills. The platform provides documentation and tutorials to assist users.

Agricultural Robot Taskmap Operation Framework (ARTOF)

The Agricultural Robot Taskmap Operation Framework (ARTOF) provides the common functionality of task map execution for a wide range of robot configurations and farming applications based on Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) positioning. The framework can be integrated into a robot platform during development or can be added afterwards with a customized after-market installation. The ARTOF framework has been integrated into several robot platforms and existing farming equipment as robot- or auto-guidance software. ARTOF includes a simulation process which enables software integration- and hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) testing. By setting the robot in simulation mode, the robot's navigation and operations are performed in a virtual environment by simulating the Gps process from the operational layer and the kinematic models from the mechatronic layer.

Summary:

- **Used by:** ILVO
- **Link to the website:** <https://artof-ilvo.github.io/>
- **License:** <https://artof-ilvo.github.io/license.html>

Autonomous driving

CARLA (UE4)

CARLA is an open-source simulation software based on the game engine "Unreal Engine 4" to take advantage of the photorealistic rendering. It is mainly used for autonomous driving vehicle simulation, but it can also be applied on other domains where autonomy behaviour relies on the perception of the environment through cameras.

CARLA supports development, training, and validation of autonomous driving systems. In addition to open-source code and protocols, CARLA provides open digital assets (urban layouts, buildings, vehicles) that were created for this purpose and can be used freely. The simulation platform supports flexible specification of sensor suites, environmental conditions, full control of all static and dynamic actors, maps generation and more.

LNE used CARLA combined with Unreal Engine 4 to set up and integrate a robotic environment that includes various scenarios for autonomous driving. CARLA provides more photorealism for a better compromise of graphical resources needed than other evaluated tools.

Case study: Using CARLA with Esimi for autonomous driving vehicle simulation

AstaZero AB utilizes CARLA within the context of autonomous driving vehicle simulation, encompassing sensor perception, robotics, planning, control, and decision-making processes. This tool is frequently employed in co-simulation with the software tool Esimini. Below is an example demonstrating how AstaZero AB leverages CARLA for testing automation functionalities.

AstaZero AB was engaged to investigate the realism required in a test environment to effectively validate and verify ADAS and AD functions and to ensure that these functions could be exposed to complex and challenging traffic scenarios. This project involved conducting both physical and digital tests based on scenarios from the Euro NCAP test protocols for AEB performance. Subsequently, a comparison and analysis of the test results were performed.

The tests were designed based on pre-defined scenarios, each one consisting of a sequence of events outlined in OpenSCENARIO files. These files detailed the actors, event triggers, and the dynamic conditions that the scenario should follow and served as the baseline for both the physical and digital test executions.

CARLA was utilized to conduct the simulated tests in co-simulation with Esmini. While Esmini managed the scenario descriptions in OpenSCENARIO, CARLA provided the simulation environment, handling the more complex physics and rendering.

The use of CARLA in this example facilitated simulation within a realistic environment, where complex physics and rendering were applied to execute tests comparable to physical tests. Given that the simulation environment is a crucial component when testing and developing algorithms intended for real-world application, CARLA proves to be a suitable tool. It offers a photorealistic simulation environment with high-quality graphics, material characteristics, and realistic traffic and pedestrian behaviours. Additionally, CARLA supports a wide range of sensors, including cameras, lidar, and radar, which can be simulated in high detail, allowing for comprehensive testing of perception algorithms and systems.

CARLA is an integral part of a comprehensive simulation toolchain, enabling performance and functionality testing at various stages of development. It plays a significant role in AstaZero AB's simulation toolchain and is frequently used in daily operations.

Summary:

- **Used by:** LNE, AstaZero
- **Link to the website:** <https://carla.org/>
- **AgrifoodTEF service that uses the tool:** Simulation-based Testing for Automated Agricultural Machines
 - <https://agrifoodtef.eu/catalogue-of-services/simulation-based-testing-automated-agricultural-machines>
- **Tool effectiveness:** Carla is mainly used for autonomous driving vehicle simulation. LNE and AstaZero give an average score of 3 in the survey question of how likely they would recommend Carla on a scale of 1 to 5 where 1 means 'not at all' and 5 means 'very likely'.
- **Integration strategies:** Carla integrates with machine learning frameworks and supports ROS, with extensive customization and integrations with other tools and systems.
- **Cost analysis:** Carla provides open-source code and open digital assets (urban layouts, buildings, vehicles) that can be used freely.
- **Assumptions:** Access to high-performance computing resources capable of handling detailed simulations.
- **Skill requirement:** Basic understanding of autonomous driving principles and simulation techniques. There is documentation and community support to help troubleshoot issues.

Farm simulation

Digital Future Farm

This digital twin represents the nitrogen cycle of an arable farm or a dairy farm. It comprises of existing process-based and new data-driven models fed with real farm data to mimic reality. It can be used by farmers and researchers to reduce the nitrogen surplus of a farm while maintaining crop yields (including grass yield for livestock).

Summary:

- **Used by:** WUR
- **Link to the website:** <https://www.wur.nl/en/research-results/research-funded-by-the-ministry-of-lnv/soorten-onderzoek/kennisonline/digital-future-farm-dff-1.htm>
- **Tool effectiveness:** Digital Future Farm is useful in modelling and simulating the nitrogen cycle within a farm. It provides insights into nitrogen use efficiency, helping to identify opportunities for reducing nitrogen surplus while ensuring optimal crop yields. WUR uses the tools as part of their design process. The tool employs modular components, representing a biophysical aspect of the farm (e.g. soil, crops, animals). Each component can be made custom to a farm and linking these components results in a full-inclusive farm-specific digital twin. A machine learning approach is discussed to be used for the twinning process.
- **Integration strategies:** Digital Future Farm integrates with data sources, including sensors and IoT devices to collect real-time data from the farm. It can also be connected with other farm management software to provide a comprehensive overview of farm operations. It also provides integration opportunity with other farm databases and external data sources.
- **Cost analysis:** Digital Future Farm is a research institute funded project leveraging existing infrastructure and open-source models to minimize costs. The primary costs involve the setup and maintenance of sensors and IoT devices, as well as data processing and analysis. The ongoing operational costs are relatively low compared to the benefits in terms of improved nitrogen management and crop yields.
- **Assumptions:** Access to accurate and reliable data from sensors and IoT devices. Adequate computational resources are required to run the models and simulations.
- **Skill requirement:** Basic understanding of the nitrogen cycle and its impact on crop production. Also, familiarity with data collection technologies. There is training and support available through WUR to help users interpret the data and implement recommendations on the simulation results.

General purpose simulation tools

ExtendSim

ExtendSim is a multi-purpose simulation tool that can be used to create dynamic models of existing or proposed processes across various fields. It supports many types of simulations including discrete event simulations. Models can be created by placing blocks from a library into a model worksheet. Blocks are connected to create the logical flow of the model.

Case study: Using ExtendSim simulations for economic assessment of pig meat processing and cutting production

This case study, from Universitat de Lleida, presents the development and adoption of a ExtendSim discrete event simulation model of a pig meat-packing plant located in Navarre (Spain). This work is described in detail in the research paper by Lluís M. Plà-Aragonés et al [Plà-Aragonés2019]. The text and figures here are extracts from that article. The simulation model was developed to represent all the tasks and pig meat cuts production performed in the plant. The development was incremental as the whole model was made of different sub-models focused on different products as for example ham, ribbon or sirloin. The main utility of the proposed model was the economic assessment of pig meat processing and cutting production.

Figure 9 Overview of the model representing the processing of carcasses.

Simulation is becoming an increasingly important tool in meat processing and meat cuts production, in which product segmentation and waste reduction are relevant issues in the food engineering field. The simulation model represents typical tasks performed in a pig meat-packing plant: processing pig carcasses in a two-sided conveyor belt and selling different meat cut products and by-products in fresh or frozen, to wholesalers and local butcheries. Hence, the goal of the model is twofold: the capability to compare different production plans of end-products for primary cuts in a working week and, even more important, a better selection of breeds for a specific production planning.

Figure 10 Comparison between incomes of two products: York shoulder and Shoulder 3D.

The simulation model was implemented in ExtendSim 9.2, an interactive general purpose simulation tool with 2D and 3D animation capabilities. The simulation environment provides the tools for all levels of modellers to create accurate, credible and usable models in an efficient way. Thus, ExtendSim facilitated every phase of the simulation project, from creating, debugging, verifying, and validating the model, to the construction of a user interface. This way, developers and target users could collaborate in the conceptual development of the model and later in the analysis of the system. A model is created by adding blocks to a worksheet and connecting them. Each block has its own functionality, dialogue, help, icon and connections. Each instance of a block in the model has its own data. The logical entity that moves through the system is referred to as an item. The items carry properties or attributes with them as they progress from one block to the next. These items are represented using data structures allowing large numbers to exist simultaneously within a model. An additional advantage for developers is the programming language to create reusable modelling blocks beyond the standard libraries provided by ExtendSim. Hierarchical blocks help to organize the model with sub-models making it more readable. For instance, each primary cut or product can be encapsulated as a sub-model into a hierarchical block.

Figure 11 Meat cutting tree for primary cuts (shoulder, cutlet, bacon, lard and ham) and by-products (lean cuts, sternum, skin cuts, fat and jowl).

The discrete event simulation is more flexible and accurate than deterministic or stationary approaches, essentially because it better captures the dynamics of the plant production and the cutting operation process. The use of a visual simulation tool like ExtendSim was essential to interact with the client company during the development of the model. The simulation model allows the plant manager to compare different products of the same family assessing a reasonable price to produce one or the other. The simulation model also gives a greater understanding of the system and can reduce operating costs by a better control of products to serve and personnel. The simulation model considered only variations in carcass weight and breeds but can explore alternative products from the same primary cut and can be easily adapted to different meat-packing plants, thanks to their modularity.

Summary:

- **Used by:** Universitat de Lleida
- **Link to the website:** <https://extendsim.com/>
- **Tool effectiveness:** Interactive general purpose simulation tool with 2D and 3D animation capabilities.
- **Integration strategies:** ExtendSim has an integrated compiled programming language and dialog editor but also support other programming languages.
- **Cost analysis:** It needs a commercial licence: <https://extendsim.com/products/purchase/pricing>
- **Skill requirement:** The platform provides documentation, tutorials and courses to assist users.

SolidWorks

SolidWorks is a professional 3D CAD (Computer-Aided Design) and CAE (Computer-Aided Engineering) software developed by Dassault Systèmes. It is widely used for designing mechanical parts, assemblies, and creating 2D drawings, as well as for simulation and product development workflows. It can be used for simulating moving parts and strength.

Summary:

- **Used by:** ILVO
- **Link to the website:** <https://www.solidworks.com>
- **Skill requirements and support:** There is online documentation and courses: <https://www.solidworks.com/support/home>. There is an online community with user group meetings, blogs, podcasts and case studies. <https://www.solidworks.com/community>
- **Cost analysis:** Commercial tool with different licensing options: <https://www.solidworks.com/how-to-buy>

Summary

The above-mentioned software packages, currently in use by our partners UniMi, Politecnico di Milano, WUR, ILVO, FBK, UDL, AstaZero, INRIA and LNE, offer unique features tailored to specific types of simulation, ranging from robotic movement and interaction to autonomous driving and crop simulation. In the survey, LNE also mentioned that they have several other simulation capabilities such as MATLAB/Simulink: Embedded solution testing without 3D Rendering (Licensed) and SCANr Studio: Close to CARLA Sim (Licensed).

Remotisation Software

Remotisation software and tools enable work from a remote location and include software and interfaces for remote access to desktops, networks and tools. Remotisation software and tools could enable remote sensing, remote monitoring, remote operation, remote tests in physical and simulated environments, remote dataset creation, or other remote services.

Remote desktop access

VNC (Virtual Network Computing) for AI Model training

VNC is a remote desktop software that enables users to access and control a computer from another device regardless of the location. This feature is beneficial for various applications, including AI model training offering secure and convenient remote access to computational resources. VNC is a graphical desktop-sharing system that enables remote control of a computer over a network. It allows users to access and interact with a machine's desktop environment as if they were sitting directly in front of it. VNC is particularly valuable as a remotisation tool for headless devices—machines that run without a local monitor, keyboard, or mouse—such as Ubuntu-based AI computers, Raspberry Pi devices, and NVIDIA edge devices. In these scenarios, VNC can be used as a tool for managing, monitoring, and troubleshooting remote systems. A key application of VNC is in environments with limited bandwidth, where video and sensor data cannot be reliably streamed to the cloud or other remote servers. In such cases, VNC allows users to remotely access, update and test AI models and check critical data locally stored on the device, such as camera feeds, sensor data, graphs, and uptime statistics. This enables the monitoring of device and AI model performance, including factors like camera cleanliness and sensor health, without the need for continuous cloud communication by the remote device. By using VNC, users can efficiently perform remote diagnostics and maintenance on devices, especially in remote or bandwidth-constrained environments, where storing and processing data locally is essential for optimal performance. VNC implementations used by EV ILVO are open source but there are also proprietary versions available.

Summary:

- **Used by:** EV ILVO
- **Link to the website:** <https://www.realvnc.com/>
- **Tool effectiveness:** VNC is effective in providing remote access to computational resources required for resource intensive AI model training. EV ILVO give a score of 5 in the survey question of how likely they would recommend VNC on a scale of 1 to 5 where 1 means 'not at all' and 5 means 'very likely'.

- **Integration strategies:** VNC can be integrated with various operating systems and platforms. It can be used alongside other remote access tools and software to create a robust remote working environment.
- **Cost analysis:** The open-source versions of VNC are free.
- **Assumptions:** Access to stable and fast internet connection to maintain seamless remote access. It assumes users have necessary permissions and security protocols in place to access remote machines. Also, adequate hardware resources on both the client and server sides are required.
- **Skill requirement:** Basic technical skills in setting up and configuring remote desktop connects. Familiarity with operating systems involved and basic understanding of network configurations. There is available documentation and communication support to help practitioners troubleshoot any issues.

Additional tools - Remote tool access

FarmBot

FarmBot is an open-source CNC (computer numerical control) farming machine and software platform that allows remote control and management for precision agriculture. FarmBot is run by Raspberry Pi computers and Arduino micro-controllers providing millimeter accuracy using the FarmBot genesis model. FarmBot can specifically be used by AgrifoodTEF partners for testing remote control operations of planting, watering, and weeding. It has a web-based interface for real-time monitoring and control. FarmBot also provides integration with sensors for soil moisture, light and temperature and can be customized with new tools and software updates.

Summary:

- **Used by:** Off-the-shelf remotisation platform.
- **Link to the website:** <https://farm.bot/>
- **Tool effectiveness:** Effective for precision, agriculture tasks, offering precise control over planting, watering and weeding. Suitable tool for testing and optimizing farming practices.
- **Integration strategies:** FarmBot has a modular design to support integration with additional hardware and software components. It can be connected to other open-source tools, platforms and various sensors for enhanced agricultural functionality.
- **Cost analysis:** The platform is open source, but the initial setup costs can include purchasing hardware components (e.g., sensors, Raspberry pi). Ongoing costs are minimal, which mainly involve maintenance and potential upgrades.
- **Assumptions:** Access to stable internet connectivity for remote control and monitoring.
- **Skill requirement:** Basic technical skills and understanding of computer hardware, software, and web interfaces to set up and customize the system. There is documentation and support community available to assist practitioners.

OpenAG

OpenAG is an initiative to develop an open-source agriculture platform for controlled environment agriculture. It allows remote control and management of various agricultural processes. The platform uses a combination of hardware and software to create 'Food computers' that can monitor and control environmental conditions with high precision. The AgrifoodTEF partners can use OpenAG facilitated with a web-based interface for real-time monitoring and control, and it integrates with various sensors for environmental factors such as humidity, temperature, and CO2 levels.

Summary:

- **Used by:** Off-the-shelf remotisation platform

- **Link to the website:** <https://www.media.mit.edu/groups/open-agriculture-openag/overview/>
- **Tool effectiveness:** Useful for research and educational purposes, allowing users to conduct experiments and optimize growing conditions for various crops. OpenAG is mainly effective for controlled environment agriculture, enabling precise control over environmental variables.
- **Integration strategies:** OpenAG integrates with a variety of agricultural sensors and can be connected to other open-source tools and platforms. The platform design is modular which allows practitioners to add new components and software updates easily, enhancing its functionality and adaptability to different research needs.
- **Cost analysis:** OpenAG is an open-source platform, and the initial expenses will include the purchase of hardware components and sensors, but ongoing costs are primarily related to maintenance and potential upgrades.
- **Assumptions:** Access to a reliable internet connection for remote control and monitoring
- **Skill requirement:** Using OpenAg requires some technical skills, including familiarity with computer hardware, sensors, and web-based interfaces. However, extensive documentation and a supportive community are available to help users with various levels of expertise.

Summary

VNC is currently being used by EV ILVO to perform AI model training. The software's ability to facilitate collaboration and resource optimization makes it an asset as remotisation tool, especially in the field of AI research and development. Farmbot and OpenAG are tools used for remote control and management. Other than that, Josephinum research is planning to introduce remotisation pipeline for their new mobile sensor platform (Infrastructure described in WP1).

Key characteristics to consider for tool selection

Table 1 illustrates the characteristics of various simulation and remotization tools mostly utilized by AgrifoodTEF partners. This table aims to provide an overview of the tools' capabilities, features, and partners involved in their implementation, supporting informed decision-making when selecting tools for specific applications in agricultural and robotics contexts. Each column represents a characteristic or feature, while each row lists a specific tool. For instance, **Error! Reference source not found.** shows tools like Gazebo, Webots, Isaac Sim, and Carla are open source, while Unity is proprietary with a free version for small-scale use. Tools like Webots, Isaac Sim, VNC and 4D-Virtualiz provide notable AI implementation capabilities. Gazebo, Webots, Isaac Sim, ARTOF, and SolidWorks are used for robot simulation. Unity, Digital Future Farm, FarmBot, OpenAG, and ARTOF are tools used in agricultural crop simulations. Unity and Carla are key examples of game engine with simulation category.

Table 1 - Tool implementation characteristics.

Tool characteristics	Open source	AI implementation	Robot simulation	Crop simulation	Autonomous vehicle simulation	Game engine with simulation	Service usage	Partners involved
Gazebo	✓		✓				✓	PM, WUR, FBK, ILVO
Webots	✓	✓	✓					UniMi, WUR
Isaac Sim	✓	✓	✓					LNE, WUR
Unity	Propriety w/ free version	✓		✓		✓		EV ILVO
Carla	✓	✓			✓	✓	Planned	LNE, AstaZer
Digital Future Farm	✓			✓				WUR
Esmi	✓				✓			AstaZero
CopeliaSim VREP	✓		✓					EV ILVO
VNC	✓	✓						EV ILVO
FarmBot	✓			✓				Off-the-shelf
OpenAG	✓	✓		✓				Off-the-shelf
4D-Virtualiz		✓	✓		✓			LNE
Unreal Engine							✓	WUR
ExtendSim								UDL
ROS2	✓		✓				✓	INRIA

ARTOF	In-house framework	✓	✓	✓			✓	ILVO
SolidWorks	Proprietary		✓				✓	ILVO

It is to be noted that many of the tools including Webots, Isaac Sim, Unity, Carla, VNC, OpenAG, 4D-Virtualiz, ARTOF support advanced simulation with AI capabilities. This table is a work in progress that provides a quick reference for selecting simulation tools based on their features and applications, making it easier to identify the most suitable tool for specific agricultural or robotics tasks.

Discussion and future work

In this report we describe the status of the survey on available tools and the knowledge base in AgrifoodTEF. The results show a mix of tools and tool chains that are currently in use by the partners. We have in this report identified fourteen simulation and three remotisation tools. The report includes detailed descriptions of the tools. For many of the tools there are case studies of how the tool is used, in an agricultural example, with analysis of the tool's pros and cons. This third version of report also includes links to AgrifoodTEF services that use the tools.

We see several avenues for expansion in the next yearly report. Besides extending the list of tools we see an opportunity to continue to evaluate the performance, usability, and reliability of the tools, based on the feedback from the end-users and the technical partners, who have tested and validated the tools in different use cases and scenarios. This evaluation could involve the assessment of the technical, economic, and environmental impacts of the tools, as well as their compliance with ethical and legal standards.

Another topic of interest is the identification of the challenges, limitations, and future improvements of the tools, as well as the lessons learned from the implementation process. The report discusses the main difficulties and issues encountered during the development and testing of the tools, as well as the possible solutions and recommendations for enhancing their functionality, quality, and usability. The report can thus reflect on the best practices and methodologies adopted for the successful execution of the project from a tool utilization perspective.

Timeframes and next steps:

Previously, in the first-year report, our primary focus was to identify which tools were already in use by the AgrifoodTEF partners and to understand their effectiveness in agriculture-specific simulation and remotisation experiments. Based on the survey findings, we initiated a series of seminars and workshops for AgrifoodTEF partners. Last year, we continued the seminar series. The seminars explored the practical applications of the different tools, discussed upcoming and possible AgrifoodTEF services, and mapped the tools to these services. The seminars served as a platform for a more comprehensive evaluation of the available tools and an opportunity to identify new tools that meet agricultural requirements. The second-year report included more detailed and specific descriptions of the tools. For many of the tools there were now case studies of how the tool is used, in an agricultural example, with analysis of the tool's pros and cons.

This year, we surveyed how the tools are used and planned to be used in AgrifoodTEF services. We collected input and initiated the work to set up a dedicated simulation and remotisation tool knowledge base specific to agricultural practices. As a future step, the knowledge base will be refined to serve as a resource for all AgrifoodTEF partners, providing detailed information on the tools' capabilities, best practices for their use, and guidelines for integration into agricultural systems.

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